

Fast online diagnosis for solid oxide fuel cells: Optimisation of total harmonic distortion tool for real-system application and reactants starvation identification

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The failure modes, fuel and air starvation, are experimentally investigated.
- A sensitivity analysis on the THD parameters is performed.
- The effect of flow configuration and operating temperature is examined.
- All the THD results are compared with EIS complemented by DRT.
- Results are presented as practical guidelines for improved SOFC system diagnosis.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the potential application of total harmonic distortion (THD), as a fast online monitoring tool, to identify the early signs of failure modes in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC). Indeed, the timely detection and identification of faults is crucial for applying mitigation strategies to avoid irreversible damage and increase the system lifetime. Two of the most common faulty conditions are considered in this work, namely fuel and air starvation. This experimental work aims at progressively triggering these errors in a controlled manner, by following different realistic scenarios, and recording THD values on a frequent basis. Several well-established laboratory monitoring tools, like electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), complemented by the distribution of relaxation times (DRT) are used to analyse and support the interpretation of the THD measurements. A sensitivity analysis on the THD parameters, namely the signal amplitude and the number of harmonics, is carried out to identify the optimal combination of parameters and achieve the best faults detectability. Finally, the impact of the fuel flow direction and the operating temperature are examined. The results of this work are summarised as practical guidelines to better employ the THD technique to identify the early warning signs of reactants' starvation.

1. Introduction

To fight climate change, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions must be drastically cut. The first step in this direction is to shift from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources. In the Paris Climate Agreement of 2015, the world has agreed to take actions to limit global warming to below 2 °C, preferably to 1.5 °C [1]. However, the energy transition also brings new challenges. First, wind and solar are highly intermittent and therefore, new technologies for energy storage at large-scale and for long periods are needed in the future. Second, certain energy intensive sectors such as steel industry, chemical industry, long-haul transport, shipping and aviation are hard to electrify and can therefore not

switch directly to renewable energy sources. Solid oxide cells, which can operate in both fuel cell mode (SOFC: solid oxide fuel cell) or electrolysis mode (SOE: solid oxide electrolyser), seem to be one of the most appealing solutions to overcome these challenges and make a successful energy transition possible. Power generation in SOFCs from hydrogen promises very high efficiencies due to operation at high temperatures. However, this technology still suffers from insufficient long-term durability, being vulnerable to many failure modes that considerably reduce their remaining useful life [2]. In this regard, online state-of-health (SoH) monitoring is crucial to extend the lifetime of this technology to reach the targeted 40,000 operating hours [3].

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To date, online monitoring tools are mainly based on voltage, current and temperature monitoring. Impedance is also monitored but its application is still widely restricted to academic research. These are basic tools that provide information about general SOFC performance. However, SOFC consists of electrodes with very complex microstructure [4,5], which results in complex process mechanisms [6,7]. Moreover, when placing a focus on SOFC technology of industrial relevance, potential, current, gas and temperature distribution can significantly change between the different cells or even along the same cell [8–10], thus impacting the overall cell and stack performance. In order to get more detailed insight into the SOFC performance and to be able to predict undesired changes as well as remaining useful lifetime, more advanced characterisation techniques can be applied. These are electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), its advanced tool distribution of relaxation times (DRT) and non-conventional total harmonic distortion analysis (THD).

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy presents an established and most commonly used a.c. (alternating current) characterisation tool for SOFCs. For the purpose of this type of measurements, sinusoidal current or voltage amplitude is superimposed to the system running under d.c. (direct current) conditions. The height of the amplitude can vary between 4%–5% of the d.c. load value, fulfilling the main requirement of the linearity of the system under investigation [11–17]. The measured impedance spectra are correlated to either different processes that occur on specific electrodes, e.g. Ni/YSZ electrode [18–20], LSM/YSZ electrode [21], or LSCF-GDC electrode [22]. The EIS measurement is often used to identify changes that occur in a running system over time, e.g. to identify degradation effects [23,24]. Moreover, EIS has also been applied to examine the effectiveness of gas cleaning and the impact of fuel purity on the SOFC performance [25]. A large frequency range from 20 mHz to 200 kHz is usually required to cover and probe all the processes with different time scales. A sufficient number of sampling points and of periods is also required to accurately reconstruct the full spectrum and improve the signal to noise ratio. Nevertheless, many processes are overlapped when applying only EIS methodology and application of additional characterisation tools is necessary in order to deconvolute all individual processes and analyse them.

Distribution of relaxation times analysis has already been carried out on different levels, starting with the electrode level and moving towards the stack level. On the smallest level, it was successfully applied to differ between the grain and bulk [26]. DRT analysis was also employed to investigate the effectiveness of different nano-catalysts to enhance reactions on the air electrode as well as their temperature dependence. In this case, it enabled to identify limitations of reactions within the air electrode, which were mainly related to gas diffusion into the porous structure at elevated temperatures and correspond to the occurrence of a new low-frequency peak. At the fuel electrode, diffusion processes were associated with frequencies between 0.5 Hz and 15 Hz, as reported in [27]. Further differentiation of electrodes and specific processes for tubular SOFCs is provided by Sumi et al. [28], which reported that air electrode processes are mainly observed in the frequency range 5–20 Hz and 10–100 kHz, while the processes on the fuel electrode are visible at 20 Hz–10 kHz 1–10 Hz and for frequencies lower than 1 Hz. A short summary of four studies [29–32] has been provided in [33], referring to five specific frequency ranges relevant for SOFCs: (i) fuel electrode diffusion for reformate fuels and air electrode adsorption/desorption for $f < 1$ Hz; (ii) for gas conversion for 1–10 Hz; (iii) both oxygen and transport related processes in the fuel electrode at 10–100 Hz and 100–1000 Hz; (iv) charge transfer in fuel electrode between 1–10 kHz; whereby for $f > 10$ kHz no corresponding process was determined. Moving towards larger sizes, in [8], investigations were carried out on both single-cell and stack level, and authors showed that it is possible to couple results obtained on the cell level with the processes that occur within stacks, whereas additional processes could be identified in stacks. A number of investigations carried out

under stationary operating conditions enabled to link specific frequency ranges with different processes that occur while operating the cells in SOFC mode. In [34], a very detailed summary of peaks observed in literature and their correlation to specific process mechanisms is reported, which can be used as a guideline while employing DRT analysis to analyse SOFC performance.

Moving towards the non-conventional total harmonic distortion methodology, most of the available studies concern lower temperature fuel cells, while the number of studies related to SOFCs is very limited [35–38]. This type of electrochemical analysis is applied for non-linear systems and the linear system analysis is thus no longer applicable in this case. Non-linear analysis was firstly employed to identify nonlinear effects that occur within the oxygen electrode, as reported in [39–41]. It is important to mention here that non-linear state was induced by superimposing high amplitudes, which disturbed the system linearity. Several processes are in general non-linear and can be observed only by applying this methodology. Moreover, it is crucial to apply this technique to identify specific degradation mechanisms (e.g., carbon deposition and Ni-reoxidation) at their preliminary stage and to classify them. Thus, the main goal when applying this online-monitoring tool for real-system application is to not disturb the linear state, but to be able to identify non-linear mechanisms that occur in the system due to undesired failure modes. The pioneering results related to industrial-size cells with a surface of 80 cm² revealed very successful application of THD to identify the most relevant failure modes and degradation phenomena in SOFCs, namely (i) fuel starvation and thus implicitly Ni-reoxidation, (ii) air starvation and thus air electrode morphology changes, and (iii) carbon deposition [17,42,43]. The THD application was even helpful to identify carbon removal and SOFC performance regeneration [17]. On the stack level, THD tool was applied to monitor the level of effective fuel utilisation [44,45].

In this study, we make a step further and provide a detailed guideline with all the necessary information (e.g. specific frequencies, amplitude to be set, relevant harmonics) on how to effectively apply the THD tool in real-life systems and how to interpret the results observed in a simple way, which is provided for the first time in the available literature. Thus, we also show that there is one simple tool available that can be used to monitor the system state-of-health in a time- and cost-efficient manner. This enables to reduce the number of other expensive monitoring tools, to identify failure modes at their very early-stage and eventually to prolong the lifetime of SOFC systems. We directly compare the EIS, DRT and THD data measured while inducing the two most relevant failure modes, fuel and air starvation. Moreover, the impact of flow conditions and temperature is examined in detail, since these can significantly influence performance of SOFC systems. Eventually, in order to perform the measurements in a correct manner and to receive meaningful information, the impact of the signal amplitude and the number of harmonics to be considered are further examined here. The application of the different tools mentioned above makes it possible to examine the process mechanisms and SOFC behaviour from different aspects.

2. Experimental setup and methods

For the purpose of this study, a single round fuel-electrode-supported cell (FESC), with an active surface area of 12.566 cm² was employed. The fuel electrode was fabricated as Ni-YSZ with a thickness of 200–300 μm. The electrolyte (YSZ), a barrier layer (GDC), LSCF:GDC composite cathode, LSCF, and current collector layer are deposited and sintered. The cells are produced by anode and electrolyte co-casting and co-sintering followed by screen-printing of the cathode layers. The 6–8 μm-thick GDC barrier layer is used to prevent chemical reactions between the 10 μm-thick YSZ electrolyte and the air electrode. To contact the fuel electrode side Ni-foam was used, whereby on the air

Fig. 1. Experimental setup used for the SOFC operation. 'WE' and 'CE' refer to working electrode and counter electrode, respectively.

side gold mesh was employed. Gold wires were employed as current collectors on both the electrode sides.

Experimental setup. Fig. 1 illustrates a schematic representation of the single cell setup used for the purpose of the experiments carried out in this study.

The setup is designed for single round cells as those described above. The fuel side is gas-tight and there are two feed lines: one in the centre and a second one along the rim of the cell, which is labelled "edge". This makes it possible to vary between two fuel flow configurations referred to as radially outward flow (centre inlet and edge outlet) and radially inward flow (edge inlet and centre outlet), the impact of which has been investigated within this study. However, it must be noted here, that this setup was predominantly designed to be used in the radially outward flow. In contrast to the gas-tight fuel electrode side, the air electrode side of the setup used is not gas-tight. There is only one inlet in the centre, but no direct outlet. Instead, the exhaust air simply leaks through the porous felt into the ambient of the furnace.

After placing the provided setup inside the furnace, a defined heating cycle must be followed to treat the glass seal. During the heating up procedure, the fuel electrode is supplied with pure N_2 gas. After reaching the desired temperature of $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the NiO in the fuel electrode is reduced to metallic Ni by gradually increasing the amount of H_2 in N_2 from zero to 200 N ml min^{-1} . During this initial startup (heating cycle and NiO reduction procedure), the air electrode is supplied with 300 N ml min^{-1} of synthetic air. One of the reasons behind setting the flow rate at the oxygen electrode higher than the one at the fuel electrode is to avoid having the fuel getting to the oxygen electrode in case of a leakage, thus protecting its steam-intolerant material.

Design of experiments. In order to investigate the impact of specific operating parameters and critical conditions on the SOFC behaviour and its reliability, a design of experiments was planned in a careful manner. Five parameters were selected to be considered as critical parameters that can influence the SOFC behaviour and their impact was thus examined in detail. These are namely: (i) fuel starvation, (ii) air starvation, (iii) THD as a function of the amplitude and number of harmonics, (iv) flow direction, and (v) operating temperature. These are also presented in Table 1, in which their application procedure is described. More detailed insight into the set parameters and specific operating environment for each of the experiments are presented in

Table 2. A number of polarisation curves and impedance spectroscopy measurements is presented here as well. The influence of each of the before-mentioned parameters on the cell behaviour and its response towards the tailored induced failure modes are discussed in detail in next Section 3.

Application and principles of online monitoring tools. Application of in-situ characterisation tools is of crucial importance to the maintenance of SOFC, since these tools allow analysing the behaviour of running systems. While the voltage monitoring and measurement of polarisation curves present the most common tools, their application provides insight into general SOFC performance and its variation. Nevertheless, in order to get better understanding of process mechanisms that occur in running SOFCs, application of more sophisticated tools, e.g. electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and its advanced tool distribution of relaxation times (DRT) as well as total harmonic distortion (THD) seems to be necessary. The application of these tools, however, must not influence the system operability or its availability.

Focusing on the EIS methodology, a sinusoidal current or voltage signal is applied and the amplitude and phase shift of the voltage or current response are measured. To obtain sufficient information about slow and fast processes that occur, the measurements are preferred to be carried out in a wide frequency range, i.e., between few mHz to hundreds of kHz. The EIS methodology requires system linearity, which means that the response to a sinusoidal signal is also sinusoidal with the same frequency. With this in mind, the amplitude applied should be small enough to assume the linearity of the measured system, but also high enough to reduce the noise/signal ratio. Increasing the amplitude improves the quality of the measurement, but intensifies the effect of non-linearity [46,47].

More detailed insight into individual processes and their specific frequencies is obtained when applying the DRT technique. This method assumes an infinite number of RC or, more recently, RQ elements, all of which have different relaxation times, connected in series. Hence, the model impedance Z_{DRT} can be written as:

$$Z_{DRT}(\omega) = R_{ohm} + \int_0^\infty \frac{g(\tau)}{1 + i\omega\tau} d\tau \quad (1)$$

with a suitable function $g(\tau)$ that describes the time relaxation characteristics of the system. The infinite distribution of elements is then discretised and fitted to the impedance measurement through weight

Table 1
List of experiments performed to investigate different failure modes.

No	Name	Description
1	Fuel starvation	Increase fuel utilisation (FU) by ...
1.1	Constant voltage	Decreasing H ₂ in N ₂ at constant voltage 0.8V
1.2	Constant composition	Increasing polarisation at constant composition H ₂ /N ₂ = 30/70
1.3	Constant current	Decreasing H ₂ in N ₂ at constant current density 318 mA cm ⁻²
2	Air starvation	Increase oxygen utilisation (OU) by ...
2.1	Varying air composition	Decreasing O ₂ in N ₂ at constant air flow rate 300 N ml min ⁻¹
2.2	Varying air flow rate	Decreasing air flow rate at constant composition O ₂ /N ₂ = 21/79
3	THD sensitivity	Change of THD Index as a function of ...
3.1	Signal amplitude	The excitation signal amplitude
3.2	Number of harmonics	The number of harmonics used for its calculation
4	Flow direction	Change the fuel flow direction to inward
5	Temperature	Lower the operating temperature

Table 2
Parameter settings for the experiments performed.

No	Parameters	Measurements
1	SOFC, 750 °C, outward, Air: 300 N ml min ⁻¹ , O ₂ /N ₂ = 21/79 <i>Constant</i>	<i>Variable</i>
1.1	0.8 V	H ₂ from 100 to 8% in N ₂
1.2	H ₂ /N ₂ = 30/70	<i>j</i> from 190 to 463 mA cm ⁻²
1.3	318 mA cm ⁻² , Amp: 5%	H ₂ from 37.2 to 20% in N ₂
2	SOFC, 750 °C, outward, Fuel: 100% H ₂ <i>Constant</i>	<i>Variable</i>
2.1	Air: 300 N ml min ⁻¹	O ₂ from 50 to 6% in N ₂
2.2	Air: O ₂ /N ₂ = 21/79	Air from 300 to 100 N ml min ⁻¹
3	Same general parameters as exp. 1	
3.1	Two points from exp. 1.3, Amp. from 1.25 to 12.5%	2 × jV, 8 × EIS
3.2	All points from exp. 1.3	None
4	Same general parameters as exp. 1 but inward jV compared with exp. 1.1, EIS and THD with exp. 1.2	3 × jV, 6 × EIS
5	Same general parameters as exp. 1 but at 700 °C jV compared with exp. 1.1, EIS and THD with exp. 1.2	3 × jV, 4 × EIS
Total: 52 × jV, 65 × EIS		

factors. By finding the best appropriate weight factors, the resistance and relaxation time of distinct processes can be identified and more easily isolated from others. However, attributing the right processes to the peaks of the DRT spectrum is all but trivial and requires a comprehensive sensitivity analysis. To compute the DRT calculation for the purpose of this study, the freely available MATLAB® toolbox DRT-tools [48] was used. More detailed description of the DRT principles as well as summary of specific frequencies from the literature related to the SOFC processes can be found in [34].

THD is a more novel and unconventional technique for online monitoring of the state of health of fuel cells. The basics of this methodology are similar to EIS, but its purpose is to evaluate the system's non-linearity. For the EIS case, voltage response of a fuel cell to a sinusoidal current signal in both the time and frequency domain is sinusoidal, because of the linear operating conditions. Thus, the response signal has the same frequency, but a different amplitude and a phase shift in comparison to the input signal. In contrast, given a non-linear operating condition, the response is not sinusoidal anymore, but distorted. The distortions can be quantified by deconvoluting the response into a sum of harmonics via Fourier transformation.

The amplitude of the fundamental frequency is denoted as Y_1 , the amplitudes of its higher harmonics as $Y_2 \dots Y_n$. The fundamental frequency is equal to the frequency of the excitation signal. The THD index is defined as the ratio of the Euclidean norm of the amplitudes Y_n of all higher harmonic frequencies ($n \geq 2$) to that of the fundamental frequency ($n = 1$):

$$\text{THD} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} Y_n^2}}{Y_1} \quad (2)$$

The first part of a THD measurement is equal to EIS. A sinusoidal signal is applied and the response is recorded. It can be acquired either in galvanostatic or potentiostatic mode. Then, the response is converted into the frequency domain via Fourier transformation, which yields the amplitudes of the fundamental and harmonics needed to calculate the THD index. Even under constant operating conditions, the THD index is yet dependent on the frequency of the excitation signal f_1 , the amplitude of the excitation signal j_{AC} or U_{AC} , and the number of harmonics n taken into account for its calculation. The amplitude of the excitation signal is often given with respect to its DC-value in relative terms, for example as Amp = j_{AC}/j_{DC} in %. The highest harmonic taken into account for calculating the THD index is denoted by n_H .

The hypothesis is that the individual processes that occur inside a cell can be identified through distortion at different excitation signal frequencies. If so, it would permit the identification of critical cell conditions and their cause via THD analysis. For example, in [43,49] it was found that carbon deposition caused a significant increase in THD at 2, 4 and 8 kHz. Once the frequencies at which distortion can be observed due to specific conditions or degradation mechanisms are mapped out, only these few fingerprint frequencies need to be checked for SoH monitoring. Therefore, THD can be much less time-consuming than EIS, which typically requires around 20 min to 1 h to obtain a full impedance spectrum. This feature is a decisive advantage of THD for real-time online monitoring purposes compared to EIS. For example, in [49] the measurement time could be reduced by a factor of 20 by using THD instead of EIS for detecting failure modes in SOCs.

In general, the higher the excitation signal amplitude, the higher the distortion of the response. This phenomenon should be clear because electrochemical cells are not linear systems, but can only be approximated as linear for a small enough polarisation range. Therefore, to

isolate the effect of the amplitude on the THD, a sensitivity analysis must be performed. In real-world operation, the amplitude of the excitation signal should be held constant, such that the relative change of THD can be effectively monitored.

Furthermore, the THD increases with the number of harmonics taken into account, as can be seen by its definition, Eq. (2). Hence, the contribution of each higher harmonic to the total THD should be investigated in order to achieve the best monitoring conditions. Since the frequencies of higher harmonics are defined as the integer multiples of the fundamental, the frequency of the 10th harmonic is already 10 times that of its fundamental. Therefore, there is a physical limit to how many harmonics can be calculated qualitatively given by the finite sampling rate of the voltage response by the measurement device. Apart from limitations given by the instrumentation, an analysis of how the THD index evolves with the number of harmonics can provide insight into how many harmonics should be considered.

In this work, a Zahner[®] Zennium electrochemical workstation was used for all EIS and THD measurements. Calibration of the device had to be performed to account for the default anti-aliasing filter, which suppresses higher harmonics to improve the quality of EIS measurements. The maximum sampling rate of the instrument is 50 kHz. The minimum sampling rate required to recover a signal must be twice the highest frequency contained in the signal. This rate is also referred to as Nyquist frequency. If the actual sampling rate is higher than the Nyquist frequency, it is called oversampling, otherwise undersampling. In light of these limitations, the manufacturer Zahner[®] recommends not to use frequencies higher than 300 Hz for the excitation signal for THD measurements with the Zennium instrument. Moreover, the instrument measures the raw harmonics of the excitation, the raw harmonics of the response and the noise (non-linearity detected in the steady-state). The true harmonics of the response can thus be calculated by correcting the raw harmonics with those of the excitation and the noise. Ultimately, Zahner[®] recommends using only the first five harmonics or less for post-processing (although ten are measured) due to precision limitations of the instrument.

3. Results and discussion

In order to examine the SOFC behaviour when operating under real-case conditions, the most relevant failure modes, namely fuel starvation and air starvation, were purposefully induced and the cell response in these specific cases was analysed. The impact of the operating temperature and flow conditions on the SOFC behaviour was further investigated. The online monitoring tools mentioned above (EIS, DRT, THD) were used for the purpose of the performance examinations. As further parameter, amplitude of the superimposed a.c. signal was varied to examine the applicability of the proposed THD approach. Its applicability was further investigated by analysing the influence of the considered number of harmonics on the information gained. The most frequent failure modes and parameters relevant while operating SOFC under real-system operating environment are analysed and discussed below.

3.1. Fuel starvation

When maintaining the SOFC efficiency, fuel utilisation (FU) is the first parameter that has to be taken into consideration. In order to maximise the system efficiency, amount of the excess fuel has to be reduced, thus increasing the FU rate. Especially when setting a focus on stacks or larger systems, the FU is expected to reach 80% or higher [50,51]. Fuel utilisation influences the temperature distribution along the stacks and, in the worst case scenario, it could cause undesired degradation effects within the fuel electrode leading to its eventual damage. In order to understand the impact of varying FU rates on the SOFC performance, its impact was carefully investigated for the purpose of this study. To this goal, hydrogen was used as a fuel and the FU impact was

examined under constant voltage, constant current and constant fuel composition conditions. The operating temperature was constant 750 °C, while the radially outward fuel flow was set with the fuel flow rate of 150 N ml min⁻¹ and the air flow rate of 300 N ml min⁻¹. The variation of the FU rate while maintaining the constant voltage, current or fuel composition is illustrated in Fig. 2(a), and more detailed discussed below. At the initial stage, polarisation curve was measured for all the fuel compositions used, thus enabling to compare FU for different operating loads.

3.1.1. Constant voltage

The operating voltage was held at a constant value of 0.8 V, while decreasing the concentration of H₂ in N₂ from 100%, over 80%, 60%, 40%, 30%, 20%, 14% and 10% down to 8%. While decreasing the hydrogen concentration, operating current density decreased and the FU rate increased from 37% for pure hydrogen up to 90% for H₂/N₂ = 8/92. In Fig. 2, the measured EIS-, DRT- and THD-values are plotted for a wide range of FU rates. The values observed for FUs up to 65% are shown on the left-hand side, Fig. 2(b), while the diagrams on the right-hand side, Fig. 2(c), show a summary of all FU values up to 90%. Such very wide spectrum of fuel mixtures and FU-rates is presented only in this figure, whereby in the remaining figures in this section only the data obtained at higher FU rates will be presented and discussed, since these are relevant for real-case application scenarios.

First, the results of EIS measurements in nominal conditions were compared to the manufacturer specifications. The values of ohmic and polarisation resistances were found in the acceptable range, thus validating the quality of the tested cell, the setup and the monitoring equipment. Furthermore, the EIS measurements were compared to published data using a similar cell from the same manufacturer [33]. As the tests presented in this article and those from the published work were carried out by using different gas compositions it was only possible to compare few parameters. For instance, at the same operating temperature of 750 °C, the measured ohmic resistance of 0.15 Ω cm² was found very close to the published one of 0.16 Ω cm².

Decreasing the amount of hydrogen in nitrogen at 0.8 V, which thus significantly dilutes the fuel, results in drastic increase of polarisation losses that can be linked to the increasing diffusion losses. For FU ≥ 86%, the frequency range should be expanded to even much lower frequencies in order to obtain the information about very slow processes that occur as a consequence of extremely increasing diffusion losses. In the DRT plots, the peaks observed at 10⁴ Hz (P5) and 10⁵ Hz (P6) do not change as a function of the FU, in comparison to the peaks observed at 10¹ Hz (P2), 10² Hz (P3) and 10³ Hz (P4). This meets the expectations that high-frequency processes, such as charge transfer (P5 and P6), are not affected by fuel starvation, whereas it impacts the low-frequency processes [33]. The peaks P3 and P4 are mainly due to electrode diffusion processes, as reported in [33]. They increase slightly and shift to lower frequencies as the FU increases. However, by far the most prominent change is the extreme increase and shift towards lower frequencies of P2, which corresponds to gas conversion processes, according to [33]. An explanation could be that the accumulation of H₂O at the TPB at high FU slows down the reaction kinetics and considerably increases the reaction barrier. Under these circumstances, it is increasingly difficult to convert the remaining fraction of H₂, which is why P2 extremely rises. For example, for 37% FU, P2 is 0.07 Ω cm² at 15 Hz, while it increased to over 5 Ω cm² at 0.9 Hz for 90% FU.

Placing the focus on the THD analysis, the distortion measured is lower than 1% in the entire frequency spectrum for FU ≤ 65%, and this THD level can be considered as noise. For FU ≥ 74%, the THD increases most notably at low frequencies (<1 Hz). The general trend is an approximately linear increase in THD with decreasing frequency, starting around 1 Hz. Although this trend is overshadowed by considerable noise/fluctuations, it appears consistent when considering the multitude of measurements (between 74% and 90% of FU). The highest THD was observed with 7.7% at 50 mHz, for FU rate of 90%.

(a) FU evolution with current density and fuel composition (left), and jV curves obtained during the fuel starvation experiments with the dots indicating the electrochemical measurement points (right).

(b) Measured EIS, DRT and THD diagrams while varying the fuel composition and FU up to 65% at a constant voltage of 0.8V.

(c) Measured EIS, DRT and THD diagrams while varying the fuel composition and FU up to 90% at a voltage of 0.8V.

Fig. 2. Electrochemical analysis of the cell performance carried out at a constant operating voltage while increasing the FU rate.

In contrast, the maximum THD for $FU \leq 82\%$ is only 3.6%, which highlights the significant rise in THD at high FU ($>80\%$). Furthermore, there are no “fingerprint” frequencies apparent, at which a consistent increase in THD due to fuel starvation in all measurements can be observed. Hence, it can be concluded that there is a general increase in THD with the decreasing frequency, especially for frequencies <1 Hz. A similar pattern was found in [42,52], in which the authors reported a

THD increase up to 6% in the low-frequency range at 100 mHz, which was observed when increasing the FU up to 85% FU (with $H_2/N_2 = 10/90$ at 0.7 V and 270 mA cm^{-2}).

3.1.2. Constant fuel composition

In the case of constant fuel composition, the fuel mixture was set to $H_2/N_2 = 30/70$ and the polarisation conditions were changed, thus

investigating the impact of the varying load and FU on the SOFC behaviour. The electrochemical characterisations were performed in galvanostatic mode with an amplitude of 200 mA, which corresponds to 16 mA cm^{-2} . With the fuel composition mentioned, the FU accounted approximately 90% at 0.7 V. Analysing the data measured, which are shown in Fig. 3(a), very similar behaviour is observed to that shown in Fig. 2. Increasing the operating current density, the overall losses increase, thus correlating to the increasing FU rate. However, the losses seem to be not so pronounced as in the previous case, which can be explained with not so intense H_2 dilution in N_2 . Since H_2 molecules are much smaller than N_2 , higher H_2 concentration and lower N_2 concentration reduce the diffusion losses. For example, for the highest FU of 90%, the polarisation resistance accounted approximately $0.84 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, while in the case discussed above it reached even a value of $2.9 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$. When comparing the DRT diagrams with each other, there is a difference and a similarity between the two experiments. The peaks P3 and P4 remain approximately constant for the constant fuel mixture, while they clearly increase with the increasing FU in experiment. These peaks can be associated with electrode diffusion processes [33], and since the composition is constant in this experiment, the diffusion characteristic changes less (despite different FU rates), compared to the previous case, in which the fuel composition changed as well. The trend observed for P2 behaves in the same manner for both the constant operating voltage and the constant fuel mixture, while for the constant fuel mixture the changes observed are less extreme, e.g. for 90% FU the peak observed was $1.5 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for constant fuel mixture in comparison to $5 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for the constant operating voltage. P2 peak corresponds to gas conversion processes according to [33] and the difference could be explained by the different fuel compositions once more. Finally, the THD trends are also similar for both cases. For FU rates $\leq 65\%$, the distortion value does not exceed 1%, which can thus be considered as a threshold for noise. The higher the FU, the higher the THD in the low-frequency spectrum. In contrast, for frequencies $> 1 \text{ Hz}$, the THD value does not increase even at very high FUs; thus, the fluctuations can be considered as noise. For frequencies $< 1 \text{ Hz}$, the THD increases with decreasing frequency and increasing FU. The maximum THD observed in this case was 5.1% at 50 mHz for 90% FU.

3.1.3. Constant operating current

Eventually, when examining the impact of increasing FU on the SOFC performance, the electrochemical characterisation was carried out while operating at a constant current density of 318 mA cm^{-2} , which corresponds to 4 A, and changing the fuel composition. The a.c. amplitude superimposed for the purpose of the examination was 200 mA, which equals to 5% of the d.c. value. The results observed are illustrated in Fig. 3(b). Yielding the FU rates between 50% and 93%, the fuel composition was varied between $\text{H}_2/\text{N}_2 = 37.3/62.7$ and $\text{H}_2/\text{N}_2 = 20/80$. For $\text{FU} \geq 80\%$, the non-linear range was observed on the polarisation curve, that can be correlated with fuel starvation effect. This behaviour is clearly visible in the Nyquist plots. Although the FU-rate increased gradually by 3% from 84% over 87% and 90% up to 93%, the polarisation impedance for the mentioned cases disproportionately increased from $1.4 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, over $1.7 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ and $2.4 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ to $4.1 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$. This shows that the increase in impedance due to fuel starvation is not linear, but exponential towards a theoretical 100% FU. The DRT observed shows that diffusion related peaks P3 and P4 increase and shift towards lower frequencies as the FU increases, similar to the behaviour under constant operating voltage. Moreover, the gas conversion peak P2 grows significantly and also shifts to lower frequencies (slower process) with increasing FU. Taking into account the measured THD values, no significant increase in the signal distortion as a consequence of severe fuel starvation is observed for $f > 3 \text{ Hz}$, as also found in the two previous cases. However, for higher FU rates, in this specific case $\geq 75\%$, an increase in THD in the low-frequency spectrum is visible. The highest THD observed in this particular case

was 9.3% at 87 mHz for 93% FU, although no distinct frequencies are apparent here.

Finally, comparing impedance spectra from the three experiments aiming to increase the FU by changing three different operating parameters, it can be concluded that the H_2 fuel concentration has the most impact on the polarisation losses for a given FU rate. Therefore, when aiming to achieve the most efficient and safe SOFC operation, high FU rates and higher H_2 concentrations are favourable. Moreover, the DRT analysis indicates a correlation of the peak observed between 1 Hz and 10 Hz with the fuel starvation effect. The height and frequency of this peak P2 are distinctly correlated, independent of the combination of FU and the fuel composition. For example, for the constant operating voltage, the amplitude of the peak P2 was observed to be $1.6 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ at 2.0 Hz (14% H_2 in N_2 and 86% FU), and for the constant fuel mixture this value was similar with $1.5 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ at 2.4 Hz (30% H_2 in N_2 and 90% FU). When taking into account the THD analysis, an increasing distortion was observed in the low frequency range. With the increasing FU rate, the THD index exponentially increased starting at approximately 1 Hz towards lower frequencies. Depending on the FU rate, different THD values were observed, with the threshold of healthy operation at approximately 0.5%–1%, consistent with that reported in [42]. The reported trend of the THD index increase in this specific frequency range is a clear indicator for the fuel starvation failure mode. Thus, the real-operation measurement can be carried out solely at a specific frequency, or two for a higher precision, within this mentioned frequency range. This will reduce the probing time, which is highly sought in real application. For instance, THD probing at 100 mHz, with a typical number of periods of 5, will require only 50 s.

3.2. Air starvation

Besides the fuel starvation effect on the fuel electrode, air starvation is considered as further failure mode that can significantly deteriorate the SOFC performance and lead to undesired morphological changes. The air starvation failure mode on the air electrode was induced by decreasing (i) O_2 concentration in a constant O_2/N_2 air flow and (ii) the air flow rate, thus also influencing the oxygen utilisation (OU) rate. The operating temperature was set to $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, following the outward fuel flow conditions with a constant pure H_2 flow rate of $150 \text{ N ml min}^{-1}$. The impact of both O_2 concentration and air flow rate on the OU rate is clearly illustrated in Fig. 4(a), in which we can see that a proper adjustment between the operating current density, the air flow rate and in specific cases, concentration of O_2 in an O_2/N_2 mixture is required to reach the optimum operation point.

In order to examine the impact of the varying O_2 concentration on the air utilisation effect and the correlating losses that occur, the O_2 concentration in N_2 was varied between 50% and 6%, whereby the OU rate thus increased from 21% up to 89%. The polarisation curve measurements illustrated in Fig. 4(b) showed that for higher O_2 concentrations (50%, 21%, 14%) the linear behaviour was observed, while for $\text{O}_2 \leq 10\%$ concentration losses were observable, which were significantly intensified with the decreasing O_2 concentration. For instance, the maximum current density reached with the air composition $\text{O}_2/\text{N}_2 = 50/50$ at 0.7 V was 1066 mA cm^{-2} , while it reached only 520 mA cm^{-2} for the composition $\text{O}_2/\text{N}_2 = 8/92$. Very similar behaviour was observed while decreasing the air flow rate (c.f., Fig. 4(b)) from 200 ml min^{-1} down to 143 ml min^{-1} resulting in increasing concentration losses and occurrence of the air starvation phenomenon. For example, when decreasing the air flow rate down to $114 \text{ N ml min}^{-1}$, a significant voltage drop was observed for current densities $< 430 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, thus referring to increasing concentration losses. The maximum current density at 0.7 V with a flow rate of $114 \text{ N ml min}^{-1}$ was merely 495 mA cm^{-2} , while it accounted 933 mA cm^{-2} for the flow rate of $300 \text{ N ml min}^{-1}$. The dots marked in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) indicate the operating points at which EIS and THD measurements were performed.

(a) Varying operating load while maintaining the constant fuel composition at $H_2/N_2=30/70$.

(b) Varying fuel composition while maintaining constant operating current density to 318 mA cm^{-2} .

Fig. 3. Electrochemical analysis of the cell performance carried out at a constant fuel mixture and constant operating current density.

More detailed insight into SOFC behaviour while decreasing both the O_2 concentration in N_2 and the air flow rate is provided by EIS and THD measurements (see Fig. 5). These were performed in galvanostatic mode under a current corresponding to a constant voltage of 0.8 V . Achieving the critical OU rate resulted in an occurrence of the third semicircle at low frequencies in both cases, while its further increase led to the increase of this newly formed semicircle. The same behaviour was observed in [42], in which the formation of the third semicircle was linked to the surge of diffusion losses on the air electrode side. Further increase of the OU rate resulted in the strong increase of this newly formed semicircle, thus referring to the extreme increase of diffusion losses. The DRT analysis showed that the phenomenon of the third impedance semicircle can be correlated to the formation of a new peak P1 at approximately 5 Hz , the amplitude of which increased significantly and moved towards lower frequencies (down to 0.1 Hz) with the increasing OU. In the case of varying O_2 concentration (c.f., Fig. 5(a)), the peak was first visible for oxygen utilisation rate of 60% at 4 Hz and then shift towards lower frequencies, i.e., 115 mHz at 89% OU. When varying the air flow (c.f., Fig. 5(b)), the peak emergence was observed for $OU \geq 62\%$. This new peak is a clear indicator for an increasing resistance due to very slow diffusion processes. Moving

towards the THD analysis, the output signal distortion is mostly pronounced at frequencies lower than 1 Hz , and its amplitude increased with the increasing OU. Two relative peaks in THD are visible for all compositions, at approximately 500 mHz and 750 mHz . For low OU rates, meaning without air starvation, the values of these peaks was found to be approximately 0.5% . This value can be considered as a threshold value. However, with the rising OU, the THD value also increases, reaching a maximum between 2% and 2.5% . Further THD increase is observed between 5 Hz and 50 mHz , the increase of which seems to follow the exponential function starting at higher frequencies and towards lower frequencies. The THD behaviour significantly differs from that observed for the fuel starvation phenomenon, and e.g. the ratio between the THD values observed at either 500 mHz or 750 mHz and 50 mHz could be a clear indicator for the air starvation failure mode.

3.3. THD sensitivity

As a crucial step, the sensitivity of THD regarding certain measurement parameters was examined. First, the behaviour of the THD index concerning the amplitude of the excitation signal is analysed. Second,

(a) Oxygen utilisation rate as a function of air flow rate, operating current density and O₂ concentration in N₂. The dots indicate the electrochemical measurement points.

(b) Polarisation curves measured while varying the air composition and flow rate to increase the OU. The dots indicate the points at constant voltage where EIS & THD measurements were performed.

Fig. 4. Polarisation curves measured when varying the O₂ concentration and air flow rate.

the evolution of the THD index with the number of harmonics taken into account for its calculation is analysed.

In order to examine the impact of the excitation amplitude on the THD values observed, the operating conditions were selected to correspond to FU values of 84% and 90%, when using the fuel compositions H₂/N₂ = 22/78 and H₂/N₂ = 20.7/79.3. The THD measurements were carried out under a load of 318 mA cm⁻² (4 A) applying the following amplitudes: 50 mA (=1.25%), 100 mA (=2.5%), 200 mA (=5%) and 500 mA (=12.5%), the results of which are shown in Fig. 6(a). While varying the amplitude, (i) THD response fluctuation and (ii) low frequency response were influenced. For the shown cases the THD obtained with the lowest amplitude (1.25%) fluctuates constantly between 2% and 3% over the entire frequency range. In contrast, the THD obtained when applying the intermediate amplitudes of 2.5% and 5.0%, fluctuates at most 1% at higher frequencies (>1 Hz) and up to 2% at lower frequencies. Moreover, the THD obtained with the highest amplitude (12.5%) appears almost like a smooth line, containing hardly any fluctuations. This trend is visible for both operating points and can be explained with the signal to noise ratio, which is an important parameter for EIS/THD measurements. If the signal amplitude is too low, the response cannot be clearly distinguished from the noise, which

results in an overly corrupted THD output. Moreover, the amplitude also affects the THD increase at low frequencies (e.g. due to fuel starvation). Setting a focus on the case with 90% FU and frequency of 50 mHz, the THD obtained with the amplitude of 12.5% accounted 16%, while the THD value obtained with lower amplitudes was observed to be lower than 6%. The same trend holds for the other operating point of 84% FU. Similarly, the THD obtained with the amplitude 5% is slightly higher on average than that obtained with 2.5%. The THD obtained with the amplitude 1.25% is hard to put in perspective as it seems to be corrupted by noise. From these considerations it can be concluded that a higher excitation signal amplitude yields a higher distortion per se. This seems plausible, bearing in mind that linearity can only be assumed for a small enough polarisation region. If the amplitude is chosen too high, the general level of distortion is high because the operation is no longer linear. In this case the THD measured may not be influenced by the failure modes that occur during the operation, but due to the measurement setting. Similar observation were made in [44], which compared the THD obtained with amplitudes of 1, 5, 10 and 20%. The THD was found to be significantly higher, as the amplitude increased. It was also found that the THD obtained with the amplitude 1% was heavily corrupted by noise. In [42], the

(a) EIS, DRT and THD results obtained when varying the O₂ concentrations between 6% and 50% and thus OU between 21% and 89%.

(b) EIS, DRT and THD results obtained when varying the air flow rate between 143 mlmin⁻¹ and 300 mlmin⁻¹ and thus OU between 44% and 90%.

Fig. 5. Electrochemical analysis of the cell performance carried out when varying the O₂ concentration and air flow rate.

amplitude with a 4% of d.c. value was used for the purpose of THD measurements. Comparing the results observed in this study and having in mind the results presented in the literature, an amplitude of 4%–5% of the d.c. value is recommended to be applied for the purpose of the THD measurements, in order to ensure the system linearity and identify only non-linearities that stem from failure modes.

In order to examine the THD sensitivity, the evolution of the THD index with the number of harmonics used for its calculation was further analysed. For this purpose, the employed data are those collected in previously described experiments at the constant operating current density (318 mA cm⁻²) and the constant amplitude (5%), but with a varying fuel composition to increase the FU. The results of calculating the evolution of the THD index are illustrated in Fig. 6(b), taking into consideration different fuel utilisation rates. In the left subplot, the normalised THD index of the entire frequency range is shown. The normalisation method is given here-below:

$$THD_{\text{normalised}}(n_H) = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{n_H} Y_n^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^5 Y_n^2}} \quad \text{with } n_H \in \llbracket 2, 5 \rrbracket \quad (3)$$

In order to aggregate the information, the average THD index per frequency decade (0.1–1 Hz, 1–10 Hz and 10–100 Hz) is shown in the right subplot. The most prominent trend is that with increasing FU, the low frequency THD index ($THD_{f:0.1-1}$) is more and more dominated only by the contribution of the second harmonic. “Contribution” means with respect to the total THD index of the first five harmonics (which is used for normalisation in Eq. (3)). For example, for 50% FU the contribution of the second harmonic towards $THD_{f:0.1-1}$ is 56%. The remaining 44% are mostly due to the third and fourth harmonics and marginally due to the fifth. In contrast, for 75% FU, the contribution of the second harmonic is 82%, for 84% FU it is 97% and for 90% FU it is 99%. Hence, it can be concluded that for high FU (>80%) the increase in THD at low frequencies (<1 Hz) due to fuel starvation stems almost exclusively from the second harmonic. All higher harmonics appear to be negligible. In contrast, the evolution of the THD index at medium (1–10 Hz) and high (10–100 Hz) frequencies appears to be rather independent of the FU. The evolution of $THD_{f:1-10}$ and $THD_{f:10-100}$ over the harmonics is similar for all FU rates. Note that at these frequencies there is no significant increase in THD due to fuel starvation. Thus,

Fig. 6. Impact of signal amplitude and the number of harmonics taken into account on the THD response.

upon considering the information from previous experiments shown above, it seems that an increase in THD in general stems predominantly from the second harmonic, while all higher harmonics are negligible. This result is in line with the findings reported in [44], where the second harmonic made up more than 95% of the total THD (of 22%

at 10 mHz, taking into account ten harmonics, at 90% FU and with an excitation signal amplitude of 10%). Finally, it can be concluded from this sensitivity analysis that the second harmonic usually contains most of the distortion of an elevated THD index, in particular for excitation frequencies lower than 1 Hz. This finding suggests that there is no need

(a) Evolution of the OCV (top) and cell temperature (middle) while changing fuel composition (bottom) in both inward 'in' and outward 'out' flow directions.

(b) jV curves, comparing the in- and outward flow directions at three different fuel compositions. The dots indicate the operating points where EIS measurements were performed.

(c) Comparing EIS measurements at different FU, for in- and outward flow directions for a fuel composition of $H_2/N_2 = 30/70$.

Fig. 7. Impact of flow direction on the cell electrochemical performance, at different fuel compositions and a constant total flow rate of 150 Nl min^{-1} .

of very fast signal acquisition equipment to use this technique, making it an affordable industrial solution.

3.4. Flow direction

This experiment aims to investigate the difference between the two fuel flow configurations: radially outward and radially inward, as depicted in Fig. 1. So far, all experiments were done with radially outward flow, for which the setup was designed. It is assumed that the radially inward flow suffers from gas leaks and less homogeneous fuel distribution over the electrode surface. To examine this hypothesis, the following experiment has been done. To begin with, the open circuit voltage (OCV) and the cell temperature were recorded, while gradually changing the fuel composition from a diluted $H_2/N_2 = 10/90$ to a rich $H_2/N_2 = 100/0$ composition. The results are shown in Fig. 7(a).

As can be seen, the OCV is consistently lower in the inward flow, by 106 mV on average. Apart from that, the trend in the OCV as a function of the composition is similar for both directions. Moreover, the rise in cell temperature with increasing H_2 content is higher in the inward flow. While changing the H_2 content from 10 to 100%, the cell temperature rose by up to 7.8 °C in the inward flow and only 2.4 °C in the outward flow. A possible explanation for both trends (OCV offset and cell temperature rise) could be related to gas leaks which are more pronounced in the inward flow. It is likely that there are small leaks, either around the circumference of the cell close to the glass sealing, or in the feed towards the edge. These leaks would predominantly affect the inward flow, for which they are located at the inlet (contrarily to the outward flow where they are at the outlet). In the case of leaks, a portion of H_2 can combust with O_2 from the ambient air thus producing steam. This reaction is exothermic and could increase the cell temperature noticeably. Moreover, a small amount of H_2O in the otherwise dry fuel can lower the OCV measurably. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that there are small leaks around the circumference of the cell and/or in the edge feed, which result in different behaviours between the flow directions.

Table 3

Comparing the OCV between the radially outward and inward flow directions for different fuel compositions.

Fuel composition		OCV	
H_2	N_2	Outward	Inward
100%	0%	1.170 V	1.086 V
60%	40%	1.214 V	1.106 V
30%	70%	1.210 V	1.097 V

To investigate the difference in electrochemical performance between the two flow configurations, polarisation curves for three different compositions were recorded and are shown in Fig. 7(b). Besides, EIS measurements at six fuel utilisation levels for the composition $H_2/N_2 = 30/70$ were done for the inward flow as illustrated in Fig. 7(c). The OCV values measured for different compositions and both flow directions are listed in Table 3. As noted before, the OCV is more than 100 mV lower in the inward flow on average. From the jV curves it can be deduced that the concentration overpotential becomes dominant at much lower current densities in the inward flow. For example, for the composition $H_2/N_2 = 60/40$, the characteristic appears approximately linear until 0.7 V for the outward flow, while the concentration overpotential is visible starting from approximately 0.77 V for the inward flow. Moreover, for the same composition, the maximum current density at 0.7 V is 773 mA cm^{-2} for the outward flow and only 502 mA cm^{-2} for the inward flow. The same trend holds for the even more diluted mixture $H_2/N_2 = 30/70$. For this composition, only 52% FU can be reached for the inward flow at 0.7 V, while the FU at this voltage is over 90% for the outward flow. This observation suggests that the fuel distribution is considerably less homogeneous in the inward flow, and high levels of local fuel starvation are experienced at lower current densities. This results in a rapidly rising concentration overpotential at a point where the overall FU is still as low as 50%.

The parameters for the EIS measurements for the inward flow are provided in Table 4 and the results in Fig. 7(c). In principle, the

Table 4

Parameters for EIS measurements: increasing the polarisation at constant fuel composition $H_2/N_2 = 30/70$, in inward and outward flow directions.

No	U_{DC} V	J_{DC} $mA\ cm^{-2}$	J_{AC} $mA\ cm^{-2}$	Amp %	FU %	ASR $\Omega\ cm^2$
1	0.875	175	16	9	34	0.92
2	0.844	206	16	8	40	1.09
3	0.818	226	16	7	44	1.40
4	0.778	247	16	6	48	2.56
5	0.734	257	16	6	50	4.33
6	0.642	267	16	6	52	6.50

trends in the Nyquist plot are similar to what has been previously observed for fuel starvation. However, since the fuel distribution is considerably less homogeneous in the inward flow, the effect of fuel starvation already appears at much lower FU rates. To sum up, the impedance for a FU of 48% in case of the inward flow approximately matches the impedance of 90% FU for the outward flow (at the same fuel composition $H_2/N_2 = 30/70$). Moreover, the lift-off of the second semicircle at low frequencies in the impedance spectrum appears more pronounced in the inward flow, which is another hint at more severe diffusion losses. In fact, the last measurement at 52% FU for the inward flow shows a new increase in impedance at low frequencies instead of following the semicircle, which is similar to a Warburg diffusion element.

In terms of frequency answer, it was found that the low-frequency negative imaginary impedance peaks of similar height (not shown in this article) are at lower frequencies for the inward flow, compared to the outward flow. For example, the peak of $0.9\ \Omega\ cm^2$ for 48% FU and inward flow is located at 200 mHz, while for the outward flow the peak of $0.8\ \Omega\ cm^2$ and 90% FU is at 400 mHz. The same trend was visible in the DRT (not shown in this article), where the gas conversion peak P2 (around 10^1 Hz) is generally located at lower frequencies in the inward flow, meaning a slower process, than in the outward flow.

It can be concluded from this investigation that the setup is well optimised for the radially outward fuel flow direction. In contrast, the inward flow direction exhibited extreme fuel starvation at relatively low current densities. Therefore, the outward flow direction is kept as the default one for all further investigations.

3.5. Temperature impact

This experiment aims to investigate the effect of the cell operating temperature on its electrochemical response. The purpose of this analysis is to check whether reducing the temperature could improve the online monitoring of fuel starvation, as an illustration. To do so, the cell was first cooled down from 750 °C to 700 °C. Then, three fuel compositions were used to compare polarisation curves and four operating points were used to compare EIS and THD measurements. The recorded polarisation curves are shown in Fig. 8(a) and the corresponding OCV values are provided in Table 5. As expected from the Nernst equation, the OCV is a few mV higher on average at the lower temperature of 700 °C. Moreover, the area specific resistance (ASR) is significantly higher at 700 °C, which is reflected in a steeper slope of the jV curve. Hence, the maximum current density at 0.7 V is considerably lower for all compositions at 700 °C compared to 750 °C. For example, for pure H_2 the current density is $933\ mA\ cm^{-2}$ at 0.7 V and 750 °C, but only $601\ mA\ cm^{-2}$ at 700 °C. However, the general shape of the polarisation curves is comparable for all gas compositions between the two different cell temperatures.

Four EIS and THD measurements were done at both 700 °C and 750 °C for the constant composition $H_2/N_2 = 30/70$ in galvanostatic mode. The exact measurement parameters are provided in Table 6, and the results are shown in Fig. 8(b). As can be seen from the Nyquist plot, the ohmic resistance increases significantly from approximately $0.15\ \Omega\ cm^2$ at 750 °C to $0.27\ \Omega\ cm^2$ at 700 °C, which shifts the entire impedance

Table 5

Comparing the OCV of different fuel compositions at 750 °C and 700 °C.

Fuel composition		OCV	
H_2	N_2	750 °C	700 °C
100%	0%	1.170 V	1.176 V
60%	40%	1.214 V	1.222 V
30%	70%	1.210 V	1.221 V

Table 6

Parameters for EIS and THD measurements: increasing the polarisation at constant fuel composition $H_2/N_2 = 30/70$, and two different cell temperatures of 750 °C and 700 °C.

No	U_{DC} V	J_{DC} $mA\ cm^{-2}$	J_{AC} $mA\ cm^{-2}$	Amp %	FU %	ASR $\Omega\ cm^2$
1	0.780	335	16	5	65	0.76
2	0.748	378	16	4	74	0.85
3	0.708	421	16	4	82	1.12
4	0.686	440	16	4	86	1.43

spectrum to the right. Moreover, the high-frequency semicircle is larger at 700 °C, while the low-frequency semicircle appears to be the same size at both temperatures.

Based on the DRT deconvolution, it can be seen that peaks P5 and P6 (around 10^4 Hz and 10^5 Hz respectively) increase noticeably at lower cell temperature. They are related to charge transfer and transport processes, which are enhanced at higher temperatures [33]. In contrast, the cell temperature does not affect the gas conversion peak P2 (around 10^1 Hz). Similarly, the THD results at both temperatures appear to overlap largely. Taking into account that the absolute level of THD is low (< 3%), the fluctuations and minor deviations between the temperatures can most likely be related to noise.

From this sensitivity analysis it can be concluded that decreasing the cell operating temperature by 50 °C does not clearly improve the detectability of fuel starvation. Indeed, the EIS measurements are very slightly more sensitive to an increase in FU at lower temperatures, whereas no clear impact was found for the THD measurements. This is explained by the fact that fuel starvation manifests as gas conversion limitations that are not thermally activated. Nevertheless, it is expected from this investigation that other degradation phenomena or faulty conditions that exhibit thermally activated limitations, like nickel agglomeration and migration for instance, could be more clearly detectable at lower operating temperatures. Finally, in real-life application, lowering the operating temperature to improve some faulty conditions' detectability would reduce the system's availability as it will no longer be running in nominal conditions. Therefore, this online monitoring strategy could be implemented for a periodic, e.g., weekly or monthly maintenance of a running system.

4. Conclusion

This work has clearly demonstrated the potential application of THD, as an unconventional online-monitoring tool, to identify the early signs of reactants' starvation in SOFC application. First, fuel starvation has been progressively triggered in a controlled manner by using three different realistic scenarios. It was found that the THD index increases significantly with FU for frequencies lower than 2 Hz, and that this increase is inversely proportional to the frequency. This allows to evaluate the FU by monitoring the distortion at specific frequencies, in a fast and reliable manner. A ratio between two THD indexes at two different frequencies can be monitored for a higher precision. Similarly, a distinct THD footprint for air starvation could be identified. It was found that the THD values measured at either 500 mHz or 750 mHz and 50 mHz could be a clear indicator for this failure mode. Furthermore, a sensitivity analysis over THD parameters revealed that the excitation signal amplitude should be high enough to improve

(a) jV curves at three different fuel compositions and two cell temperatures, 750 °C and 700 °C. The dots indicate the operating points where electrochemical characterisations were performed.

(b) EIS measurements (left) complemented by DRT deconvolution (middle) and THD analysis (right) for a fuel composition of $H_2/N_2 = 30/70$.

Fig. 8. Impact of temperature on the cell electrochemical performances, at different fuel compositions and a constant total flow rate.

the signal to noise ratio, and low enough to avoid the intrinsic non-linearity of the cell. The absolute percentage may change depending on the size of the investigated device (cell, short stack, or full-stack), because they have different dynamic responses. Nonetheless, taking into account results observed in this study, amplitudes around 5% can be recommended. Moreover, this sensitivity analysis revealed that the THD index stems mainly from the second harmonic in the Fourier decomposition in the case of fuel starvation (>80% contribution). This finding suggests that there is no need of very fast signal acquisition equipment to use this technique, making it an affordable industrial solution. Furthermore, reducing the operating temperature did not clearly improve the detectability of reactants' starvation as they are not thermally activated processes. Nevertheless, this strategy could be relevant for other thermally-activated degradation phenomena, such those that affect the triple phase boundaries or involve secondary phase formation. Finally, the results of this work have been presented in the form of practical guidelines to better employ the THD monitoring technique for early-stage failure detection.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Hamza Moussaoui: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Gerald Hammerschmid:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Jan Van herle:** Funding acquisition, Supervision, Reviewing. **Vanja Subotić:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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